

Efficient (In-)Consistency Management for Heterogeneous Repositories

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Abstract

When a group of authors collaboratively edits interrelated documents, consistency problems occur almost immediately. Current document management systems (DMS) often lack adequate facilities for consistency management. We extend traditional DMS by explicit formal consistency rules. In contrast to many other approaches, we permit inconsistencies and present the consequences to the user, which is vital for flexible document management and information management. Based on a novel semantics our tools pinpoint inconsistent document parts and tell precisely when, where, and why a repository is inconsistent.

In this paper we focus on a key issue: efficient techniques for consistency rule evaluation. Our strategy is known from databases: (1) static analysis characterizes and simplifies consistency rules and (2) at run-time rules are evaluated incrementally. The major differences to databases are that we consider informal documents and explicitly allow inconsistencies. Consequently, we lack formal update descriptions and cannot rely on consistency prior to updates.

The contribution of this paper is to incrementally evaluate consistency rules in the presence of previous inconsistencies. We have implemented our techniques in a revision control system. Our experiments show that efficient incremental evaluation is the key to make our approach viable.

Key words *information management, document management, consistency, incremental evaluation*

1. Introduction

Usually, a multitude of authors is involved in producing larger bodies of writing that contain many interrelated documents, such as books, technical documentations, or software specifications. Managing, e.g., document versions and author access rights mainstream DMS store documents in a repository. In order to produce an overall con-

sistent work authors have to spend much time re-reading and revising their own and related documents. Worse, each check-in to the repository can violate consistency again.

In [17] we proposed the use of explicit formal consistency rules that may be violated to manage consistency in heterogeneous repositories. Our approach allows inconsistencies, which is vital for flexible information management [10]. We employed a typed first-order temporal logic with linear time and extended traditional boolean semantics to generate consistency reports, which pinpoint inconsistent document parts.

Speed is a key to user acceptance. After a check-in to the repository, authors want to know almost immediately whether this check-in is accepted and how it meets the consistency rules. In this paper we address the issue of *efficiently* evaluating first-order linear temporal formulae against a heterogeneous repository while retaining our tolerant semantics. We improve efficiency by two measures: First, we reduce checking complexity by static analysis that is performed prior to actually evaluating consistency rules. Second, we reduce the complexity of the checking algorithm itself during evaluation. Static rule analysis attempts to decrease the number of rules to be re-evaluated at a check-in by “localizing” and filtering, and to decrease the static computational complexity of a rule by rewriting. Our evaluation algorithm dynamically reduces quantifier domains. Since we allow inconsistencies in previous repository states we employ an incremental algorithm that makes heavy use of previous consistency reports.

This paper¹ is organized as follows: Sect. 2 and Sect. 3 summarize our extensions to a typical DMS, the abstract syntax of consistency rules, and our tolerant semantics. Sect. 4 forms the heart of this paper by detailing our techniques to speedup evaluation of consistency rules. Some related work is discussed in Sect. 5. Sect. 6 draws final conclusions and shows directions for future research. Throughout we use the following example from [17]. In practice we come across far more complex examples of

¹A more detailed version of this paper is published as [16].

(1) At each time links must be valid:
 “At any time t we have for all documents x at t that for all their referenced keys k there exists a key definition d (in one of the resolvers) for k and there exists a manual m with name and kind as defined by d .”

$$\forall t \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall x \in \text{repDs}(t) \bullet \forall k \in \text{refs}(x) \bullet$$

$$\exists d \in \text{concatMap}(t, \text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t)) \bullet$$

$$\exists m \in \text{repManDs}(t) \bullet k = \text{key}(d) \wedge$$

$$\text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d) \wedge \text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)$$

Figure 4. Example rule r_1

Doc	= Doc	{id:String, time:Time}	documents
ManD < Doc	= Man	{kind:String}	manuals
ResD < Doc	= Res	{kDefs:[KDef]}	key resolvers
KDef	= KDef	{key, kId, kKind:String}	key definition

Figure 5. Example type definitions

Each symbol has a unique name. Due to their first temporal parameter the meaning of partially temporal function symbols and predicate symbols may change over time. For comparing timestamps we require a predicate symbol \leq , interpreted by a total ordering relation, thus facilitating linear time logic.

Our static type system comprises record and variant types. Cardelli-style subtypes prove practical for document management – so we can easily model document subsets from our example via subtypes. We define a document type `Doc` carrying the name and the check-in time of a document; all other document types must be subtypes of `Doc` and play an important rôle in incremental evaluation.

Example 2 The rule designer formalizes the first rule as shown in Fig. 4. Rule r_1 first quantifies over all states in the repository, provided by `repStates`. The function `repDs` returns the current documents for a state t . For each document x the variable k comprises the referenced keys, computed via `refs`. Key definitions in the resolvers are computed via the higher-order function `concatMap`. It applies `kDefs` to t and each key resolver, computed via `repResDs(t)`. Applied to a key resolver `kDefs` returns its key definitions in a list. Finally, the resulting lists are concatenated. Thus d ranges over the key definitions from all key resolvers. The variable m ranges over all manuals at the state t , computed via `repManDs`. For partially temporal symbols that do not depend on time, e.g., `refs`, we can omit the temporal parameter.

The language designer defines the types shown in Fig. 5, where we omitted the definitions of the list type `[]` and the type `String`. A subtype relation between record

```

State 1 doc.txt  as shown in manual kaA1c3 ...
      keys.xml <kDef key="kaA1c3"
                kId="man1.xml"
                kKind="technical M." />
      man1.xml <man kind="technical M."> ...
State 2 man1.xml <man kind="field M."> ...
  
```

Figure 6. Example repository check-ins

types is denoted by $<$. Record labels induce new partially temporal function symbols, e.g., `kDefs`. We can use them as arguments of higher-order functions, e.g., in `concatMap(t, kDefs, repResDs(t))`. For brevity we omit the formal declarations for function symbols and predicate symbols used by our example. \square

Our tolerant semantics pinpoints the trouble spots that make a repository inconsistent w.r.t. the rules formalized. The basic goal of our semantics is to provide authors with as few as possible information that precisely characterize *when*, *where*, and *why* a repository is inconsistent. Extending `xlinkit` [8] we compute for each rule a *consistency report* containing a boolean result (representing boolean truth semantics) and a diagnosis set. Each diagnosis consists of a consistency flag, a variable assignment, fulfilled predicates, and failed predicates. A diagnosis (C, as, ps_t, ps_f) reads: “The processed formula is fulfilled (Consistent) for variable assignments as due to true predicates ps_t and false predicates ps_f .” Similarly (IC, as, ps_t, ps_f) indicates that the formula is not fulfilled (InConsistent). The assignment as maps variables to concrete values, e.g., timestamps or documents. Due to temporal quantification it tells *when* and *where* a rule is not fulfilled. The predicate sets ps_t and ps_f describe *why* a rule is not fulfilled. Evaluating rule r_1 illustrates the above:

Example 3 For brevity we omit Haskell sources of function and predicate symbol implementations. Fig. 6 shows a small repository containing a text document, a key resolver, and a manual the kind of which changed during the transition from state 1 to state 2. The report for the rule r_1 reflects the inconsistency introduced at state 2.

$$\left(\text{False}, \left\{ \left(IC, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} t \mapsto 2, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}, \\ x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\} \end{array} \right\} \right), \left(\emptyset, \{\text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)\} \right) \right\} \right)$$

The assignment above lacks d and m – the repository is inconsistent w.r.t. r_1 for all possible assignments to d and m . The report also lacks $k = \text{key}(d)$ and $\text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d)$ – the key resolver contains `kaA1c3`, but its definition is inconsistent. This means that manuals m with the correct name were found but that they have the wrong kind: The first step of the link is consistent, the second step is inconsistent. \square

state	repository changes	rules	IC	CPU time
1	txt: 1n, key: 1n, man: 9n	r_1, r_2	0	5.23 sec.
2	txt: 1c, 4n	r_1, r_2	4	13.48 sec.
3	man: 2c	r_1, r_2	14	18.95 sec.
4	man: 2c	r_1, r_2	19	26.38 sec.
5	txt: 1c	r_1, r_2	21	33.40 sec.
6	txt: 1c	r_1, r_2	26	41.15 sec.
7	key: 1n	r_1, r_2	31	47.11 sec.
8	man: 1n	r_1, r_2	35	57.34 sec.
9	key: 1c	r_1, r_2	36	67.14 sec.

Figure 7. Brute force checking performance

We have implemented our consistency checker into the revision control system darcs [15]. Evaluating our example brute force is by far not satisfactory. Fig. 7 sketches the development of a “toy” repository, which we shall use throughout.² The second column shows how many documents were added (n) or changed (c) during a state transition. We use man for manuals, key for key resolvers, and txt for other text documents. The third column contains the rules evaluated. Inconsistencies found are summarized in the fourth column. The final column shows the CPU time needed for the consistency check. To great extent CPU time depends on the repository state because brute force checking evaluates every repository state.

In order to make our approach viable it absolutely necessary to develop methods that decrease evaluation time.

4. Speeding up Consistency Checking

In this section we consider static and dynamic methods to decrease the computational complexity of evaluating first-order consistency rules. For simplicity we shall neglect the individual computational complexity of functions and predicates. We designed our methods to make as few as possible assumptions to the underlying DMS. We only require (1) a repository to access past documents, (2) a locking mechanism that avoids updates during a consistency check, and (3) that the DMS signals the documents added or changed by an update. Since we do not require a specific document model our techniques also apply to revision control systems, such as CVS or darcs. Due to space restrictions we exemplify our techniques for rule r_1 only.

4.1. Static Analysis

Static analysis tries to localize and simplify consistency rules *before* they are evaluated against a repository. It is performed almost exclusively on a syntactical level. *Localizing* a rule means to associate it with the set of those documents that can possibly affect it – thus reducing the number

of rules to be re-evaluated at a repository check-in. A rule is *simplified* by minimizing its quantifier nesting and thus reducing the static evaluation time complexity. We shall only sketch our methods here because they are straightforward adaptations to techniques known from databases [3, 4].

When the DMS signals that the repository has changed, we want to re-evaluate only those consistency rules that might be affected by these updates. With each rule we associate a set of affected documents because we also want to extend revision control systems, such as CVS, that lack a formal document model.³ Rule localization depends on appropriate metadata for functions and predicates. Static Haskell code analysis helps the language designer to add these metadata. Then, a straightforward algorithm associates a consistency rule with a document set. For example, it associates the rule r_1 with all text documents and all XML documents ($*.txt | *.xml$). That is because `repDs` accesses text documents and XML documents ($*.txt | *.xml$), `repManDs` accesses manuals only ($man*.xml$), `repResDs` accesses key resolvers only ($key*.xml$), and `refs` accesses the documents of its second argument only.

The computational cost to evaluate a consistency rule depends on the deepest quantifier nesting, which is minimal if the scope of each quantifier is minimal. Such formulae are called *miniscope* [2]. Consider the rule r'_1 :

$$r'_1 = \forall t \in \text{repStates} \bullet \forall x \in \text{repDs}(t) \bullet \forall k \in \text{refs}(x) \bullet \\ \exists d \in \text{concatMap}(t, \text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t)) \bullet \\ k = \text{key}(d) \wedge \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \exists m \in \text{repManDs}(t) \bullet \text{id}(m) = \text{kId}(d) \wedge \\ \text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d) \end{array} \right)$$

Here, the existential quantifier over m was moved into the conjunction, which is sound because $k = \text{key}(d)$ does not contain m . Since the existential quantifier has a smaller scope now, r'_1 can be evaluated faster than r_1 . We adapt the techniques in [2] to convert our rules to miniscope. Miniscoping also removes implications, pushes negations into formulae, and “flattens” nested conjunctions and disjunctions. Our incremental evaluation algorithm benefits from these simplifications.

How does static analysis improve evaluation time? The second last column of Fig. 10 (see end of Sect. 4.3) shows some benefits, especially when the second rule is not re-evaluated. Improvements achieved by miniscoping can be seen in states where both rules are re-evaluated. The results are, however, unsatisfactory: Still, rule evaluation time depends on the repository state. One of the major reasons is that we access documents at *previous* repository states. Usually, the DMS rebuilds these documents step by step using state transition descriptions, e.g., diffs or patches.

³In more sophisticated DMS we could define document classes (so-called stereotypes) and associate these classes with consistency rules.

²Tests are performed on a Dell X200 laptop; 800 MHz PIII CPU.

Next, we discuss dynamic methods, which attempt to avoid accessing past document versions.

4.2. Incremental Evaluation

The major goals of incremental evaluation are: (1) access only current document versions and (2) as far as possible access changed or new documents only. A very simple strategy would be the following: Static rules quantify only once over all repository states and lack calculations of time, e.g., r_1 . Thus we can copy the report from the previous evaluation and evaluate the rule w.r.t. the new repository state only. This, of course, breaks down for temporal rules (e.g., r_2), which relate different repository states.

We, therefore, developed a general technique that also applies to temporal rules. As usual, it is most challenging to balance the speedup against the space needed for storing auxiliary information. Our approach needs only few additional information [16]. Instead it exploits previous reports to re-evaluate rules only w.r.t. a part of the documents they affect. Our strategy is as follows:

1. Keep the old report from the last evaluation.
2. If possible re-evaluate a rule only on new or changed domain values. For old domain values copy the relevant part from the old report.

A fundamental prerequisite to incremental evaluation is that the consistency report of a rule remains constant if its quantifier domains remain constant. This requires that the result of a function or predicate depends on its parameters only – a feature called *referential transparency* in functional programming. In general, Haskell guarantees referential transparency. Since in our approach language designers use Haskell to define symbol semantics, the strategy above is sound. A notable exception is the “unsafe” function `repStates`, which is not referentially transparent because it reads the number of already performed check-ins directly from the repository [16].

To support incremental evaluation, the language designer associates with each function symbol and each predicate symbol those parameters it actually depends on. For example, the partially temporal function symbol `refs` does not depend on its temporal parameter. Within rules a straightforward algorithm marks subformulae and quantifier bounding terms with the variables they actually depend on. Below, we have marked rule r_1' where variables appear as superscripts. (* means that a subformula or quantifier bounding term contains `repStates`, i.e., it is unsafe.)

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall^* t \in \text{repStates}^* \bullet \forall^t x \in \text{repDs}(t)^t \bullet \forall^{t,x} k \in \text{refs}(x)^x \bullet \\ & \exists^{t,k} d \in \text{concatMap}(t, \text{kDefs}, \text{repResDs}(t))^t \bullet \\ & k \stackrel{k,d}{=} \text{key}(d) \wedge^{t,k,d} \\ & \left(\exists^{t,d} m \in \text{repManDs}(t)^t \bullet \text{id}(m) =^{d,m} \text{kId}(d) \wedge^{d,m} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \text{kind}(m) =^{d,m} \text{kKind}(d) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8. Incremental evaluation of rule r_1'

In order to narrow quantifier domains we partition them into four sets: *new* contains new values, *chg* contains changed values, *del* contains deleted values, and *old* contains values that remained constant. Finally, we extend variable assignments, which map variables to values, to also mark variables as new and old, respectively.

The central idea behind our incremental evaluation algorithm is to *re-evaluate a subformula only if it depends on a variable marked as new* in the current assignment or if it contains an unsafe function or predicate. If a subformula depends only on old variables and contains only referentially transparent functions and predicates, we copy part of the old report and abort re-evaluation of this subformula.

Before detailing the formalism we illustrate our incremental strategy with an example:

Example 4 Consider a check-in of a new manual `man2.xml` at state 3 also referencing the key `kaA1c3`:

```
<man kind="field M.">
... <see>kaA1c3</see> ... </man>
```

We have to re-evaluate both rules. Fig. 8 shows how our incremental algorithm evaluates rule r_1' . In the tree vertices represent conjunctions, disjunctions, or quantifier domains where old values are grey and new values are black. A path from the root to a leaf can be seen as an assignment.

Evaluating t 's domain results in the sets $new = \{3\}$, $chg = \emptyset$, $old = \{1,2\}$, and $del = \emptyset$. Since t 's subformula depends only on t and is referentially transparent we can abort re-evaluation for values in *old*. Instead, we copy relevant states from the old report \mathbb{R} , which results in a true report (True, \emptyset) for $t \mapsto 1$ and the following report for $t \mapsto 2$ (assignments in reports lack variable markers):

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left\{ \text{IC}, \{x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}, \right\} \right) \right)$$

The report above lacks the binding $t \mapsto 2$, which is removed while copying. When we finally evaluate t 's quan-

$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_{(TL,I)}^b \llbracket p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta & \quad (p \text{ partially temporal}) \\ & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \{(C, \emptyset, \{p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)\}, \emptyset)\}) \\ & \quad \text{if } (\mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \eta, \dots, \mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e_n \rrbracket \eta) \in p^{\dot{A}} \\ & \quad (\text{False}, \{(IC, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{p(e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n)\})\}) \\ & \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \text{where } \dot{A} & = I(\mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_0 \rrbracket \eta); \\ \mathcal{R}_{(TL,I)}^b \llbracket p(e_1, \dots, e_n)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta & \quad (p \text{ temporal}) \\ & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \{(C, \emptyset, \{p(e_1, \dots, e_n)\}, \emptyset)\}) \\ & \quad \text{if } (\mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \eta, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{TL} \llbracket e_n \rrbracket \eta) \in p^{TL} \\ & \quad (\text{False}, \{(IC, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{p(e_1, \dots, e_n)\})\}) \\ & \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \phi \wedge^{xs} \psi \rrbracket \eta & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad r_\phi \otimes r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False} \\ & \quad r_\phi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{False} \\ & \quad r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False} \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \text{where } r_\phi & = \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{False}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta; r_\psi = \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{False}} \llbracket \psi \rrbracket \eta \\ \mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \phi \vee^{xs} \psi \rrbracket \eta & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad r_\phi \oplus r_\psi \quad \text{if } \text{fst}(r_\phi) = \text{fst}(r_\psi) = \text{False} \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \text{where } r_\phi & = \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{False}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta; r_\psi = \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{False}} \llbracket \psi \rrbracket \eta \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket (\neg\phi)^{xs} \rrbracket \eta & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad \overline{\text{flip}}(\mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta) \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \forall^{xs} x \in e \bullet \phi \rrbracket \eta & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad \oplus(F) \quad \text{if } F \neq \emptyset \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \text{where } (new, chg, old, del) & = \mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta \\ rs & = \{ (v, \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{True}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, o)]) \mid v \in old \} \cup \\ & \quad \{ (v, \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{True}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, n)]) \mid v \in new \cup chg \} \\ F & = \{ \text{push}(x \mapsto (v, o), r) \\ & \quad \mid (v, r) \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{False} \} \\ \mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \exists^{xs} x \in e \bullet \phi \rrbracket \eta & = \text{copy}(\mathbb{R}, \eta) \quad \text{if notEval}(b, xs, \eta) \\ & \quad (\text{False}, \emptyset) \quad \text{if } T = F = \emptyset \\ & \quad (\text{True}, \emptyset) \quad \text{if } T \neq \emptyset \\ & \quad \oplus(F) \quad \text{otherwise} \\ \text{where } (new_0, chg, old_0, del) & = \mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta \\ new & = new_0 \cup old_0 \cup chg \quad \text{if } del \neq \emptyset \text{ or } chg \neq \emptyset; \\ & \quad new_0 \quad \text{otherwise} \\ old & = \emptyset \quad \text{if } del \neq \emptyset \text{ or } chg \neq \emptyset; \\ & \quad old_0 \quad \text{otherwise} \\ rs & = \{ \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{True}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, o)] \mid v \in old \} \cup \\ & \quad \{ \mathcal{R}_A^{\text{True}} \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta[x \mapsto (v, n)] \mid v \in new \} \\ T & = \{ r \mid r \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{True} \} \\ F & = \{ r \mid r \in rs \text{ and } \text{fst}(r) = \text{False} \} \end{aligned}$
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Figure 9. Incremental evaluation algorithm for annotated rules (for auxiliary functions see [16])

tifier the binding for t is “pushed” in again. Note that the domain of k contains only old values when it is evaluated for $x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}$ because the bounding term $\text{refs}(x)^x$ depends on the old variable x only. Re-evaluating r'_1 for $t \mapsto 3$ results in:

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left((IC, \{x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}), \right) \right), \left(\left(\emptyset, \{\text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)\} \right), \left((IC, \{x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{man2.xml}, \text{time} = 3\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}), \right) \right) \right)$$

Pushing the bindings $t \mapsto 2$ and $t \mapsto 3$ into the reports above results in the final report:

$$\left(\text{False}, \left(\left((IC, \{t \mapsto 2, x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}), \right) \right), \left(\left(\emptyset, \{\text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)\} \right), \left((IC, \{t \mapsto 3, x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{doc1.txt}, \text{time} = 1\}\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}), \right) \right), \left(\left(\emptyset, \{\text{kind}(m) = \text{kKind}(d)\} \right), \left((IC, \{t \mapsto 3, x \mapsto \{\text{id} = \text{man2.xml}, \text{time} = 3\}\}, k \mapsto \text{kaA1c3}\}), \right) \right) \right)$$

Due to our strategy we copied some part of the old report during evaluation of the *new* repository state ($t \mapsto 3$). Notice, however, that bindings to the current state 3 are lifted to the previous state 2 because the old report cannot contain a binding $t \mapsto 3$. \square

4.3. An Incremental Evaluation Algorithm

In this section we formalize our algorithm – an incremental variant of brute force evaluation shown in [17].

As usual, we interpret temporal formulae in *first-order temporal structures* $A = (TL, I)$, which consist of (1) a timeline TL interpreting temporal types, fully temporal predicate symbols, and fully temporal function symbols, and (2) a function I associating a time w with a *non-temporal* structure $\dot{A} = I(w)$ interpreting non-temporal types, partially temporal predicate symbols, and partially temporal function symbols. The function $\mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta$ calculates the domain e of a quantified formula w.r.t. a temporal structure A and an assignment η . It results in the four sets *new*, *chg*, *old*, and *del* [16]. In contrast, $\mathcal{V}_A \llbracket e \rrbracket \eta$ performs classic value computation of terms outside domains.

Our incremental report generator $\mathcal{R}_A^b \llbracket \phi \rrbracket \eta$ (see Fig. 9) is initially applied to an empty assignment. The boolean parameter b determines whether the evaluated subformula is immediately below a quantifier. Only then it is sound to copy part of the old report because conjunctions and disjunctions combine reports non-trivially. Since miniscoping flattens conjunctions and disjunctions this restriction has only low impact. Also due to miniscoping, we can neglect negations of non-atomic formulae. This simplifies our algorithm. For readability we introduce a global variable \mathbb{R} , which represents the old report.

state	repository changes	rules	CPU time (4.1)	CPU time (4.1 & 4.3)
1	txt: 1n, key: 1n, man: 9n	r_1, r_2	4.44 sec.	4.47 sec.
2	txt: 1c, 4n	r_1	9.55 sec.	2.33 sec.
3	man: 2c	r_1, r_2	15.25 sec.	6.45 sec.
4	man: 2c	r_1, r_2	20.40 sec.	6.58 sec.
5	txt: 1c	r_1	23.46 sec.	2.68 sec.
6	txt: 1c	r_1	27.98 sec.	2.53 sec.
7	key: 1n	r_1	32.50 sec.	3.09 sec.
8	man: 1n	r_1, r_2	44.66 sec.	4.01 sec.
9	key: 1c	r_1	45.34 sec.	3.61 sec.

Figure 10. Improvements by static analysis (4.1) and incremental evaluation (4.3)

For every formula $\text{notEval}(b, xs, \eta)$ determines whether it appears immediately below a quantifier, it depends only on variables xs marked as old in the current assignment η , and contains referentially transparent functions and predicates only. In this case we copy the relevant states from the old report \mathbb{R} .⁴ (copy replaces bindings to the current repository state with bindings to the previous repository state.)

The most important case is an existentially quantified formula. Due to miniscoping all quantifiers occur positively in a formula. So existential quantifiers cannot appear “disguised” as negated universal quantifiers. We first compute the domain, resulting in the four sets new_0 , chg , old_0 , and del . The general idea is to mark the values in new and chg as new (n) and the values in old as old (o). Then the subformula is evaluated for possible assignment extensions to these values ($\eta[x \mapsto (v, n)]$ and $\eta[x \mapsto (v, o)]$, respectively). Alas this is only sound if no values were changed or deleted in the domain, i.e., $chg = del = \emptyset$. Naturally, an existentially quantified formula can become false just from deleting values in its domain. Adding new values to the domain cannot falsify an existentially quantified formula. Consequently, if either chg or del contains values we must mark every domain value as new in the assignment extensions. So the worst cases for incremental evaluation are changed or deleted values in domains of existential quantifiers.

We could overcome the restrictions above by adding explicit information to the reports, which values in the domain of an existential quantifier made a rule consistent or inconsistent. We would really like to do so but we experienced that reports become extremely large when we stored these additional values. Consequently, our tradeoff is to avoid storing these additional information and accept

⁴A state in the old report may contain an assignment more detailed or more general than η . Therefore, we copy all states containing assignments that subsume or are subsumed by η . An assignment as_1 subsumes an assignment as_2 if each variable binding in as_1 also occurs in as_2 , where we neglect variable markers.

that evaluation of existential quantifiers can be slower than evaluation of universal quantifiers. Universal quantifiers do not suffer from changed or deleted domain values because our reports already store the values that make a rule inconsistent – they pinpoint inconsistencies.

Let us return to our toy repository. What does incremental evaluation buy? Fig. 10 shows the performance of our consistency checker using both static analysis and incremental evaluation. Now, evaluation time depends rather on the changed content than on the repository state. Notice that except for states 3 and 4 every evaluation is faster than the initial evaluation although the repository grows. The simple initial strategy from Sect. 4.2 cannot achieve this.

5. Related Work

Since managing consistency is a fundamental problem a huge body of related work exists; see, e.g., [8, 17]. Here, we focus on incremental consistency checking and discuss only some closely related work in this area. In contrast to our approach, most of the other incremental approaches enforce consistency and thus benefit from total satisfaction of consistency rules prior to consistency checking.

Incremental programming languages [6] provide a uniform approach to incremental computation. They attempt to minimize redundant computation provided that a program runs repeatedly on slightly different inputs. To produce the current results of a program run, incremental computation uses previous results, differences between previous inputs and current inputs, and auxiliary information. We can regard quantified formulae as “functions” having the quantifier domain as input, which is reduced during incremental evaluation.

From its origin, the database community has been striving for efficient algorithms that check integrity constraints [14, 3, 18, 4]. Usually, these approaches employ the following techniques: *Compile-time* analysis simplifies integrity constraints and identifies update types that might violate constraints. *Run-time* approaches use previous results to avoid re-computation. In the context of first-order logic they reduce quantifier domains.

In general, we follow the database community approach but lack a formal database schema, formalized updates, and consistency prior to updates. This makes our approach more complicated. We cannot benefit from constraint subsumption because this is undecidable in our rule language; miniscoping performs only some very simple subsumption analysis. Localizing rules roughly corresponds to using update information in [4]. In order to gain the fine granularity needed for database approaches we parse documents. Consequently, our approach would lack efficiency if we implemented only strict rules. Tolerating inconsistencies, however, allows to defer evaluation of weak rules and to

acknowledge or prohibit a check-in after the strict consistency rules have been evaluated. In (temporal) databases the problem of efficiently storing and managing historical database states arises. In our setting, historical repository states are already stored and managed by the DMS.

Recently, incremental evaluation techniques were used by the XML community to maintain consistency w.r.t. user defined rules [5]. The consistency checking toolkit xlinkit [11] uses static analysis to filter consistency rules relevant to document changes and a treediff algorithm to determine document parts that have to be re-checked. Its tolerant view of consistency distinguishes xlinkit from other approaches and makes it closer to our approach. By allowing distribution and avoiding a history-aware repository, xlinkit cannot implement temporal consistency rules and lacks several incremental techniques we can benefit from.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

We have shown how first-order consistency rules can be evaluated efficiently by employing incremental techniques. Exploiting domain knowledge supplied by the language designer, we statically analyze consistency rules to (1) associate with each rule a document set the rule depends on, and (2) miniscope rules to reduce their static evaluation time complexity. At run-time we re-evaluate a rule only on new and changed documents if possible. It turned out that Haskell's referential transparency provides fundamental support for the soundness of our techniques. We provided concrete performance measurements proving that static analysis combined with incremental evaluation provides significant speedup compared to brute force evaluation. We conjecture that our incremental evaluation algorithm could be of value in other research areas.

In the future, we will focus on fine tuning our incremental approach based on further experiments. Sophisticated caching techniques, which consider function and predicate properties (such as transitivity), become important when we evaluate complex functions and predicates. Function and predicate properties also may prove useful for taking advantage of rewriting techniques in the Haskell compiler GHC [13]. Furthermore, we develop strategies to suggest *reasonable* repair actions that can resolve inconsistencies.

Extending our previous work [17], the contributions of this paper provide the key to make our approach to consistency management viable.

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